

Electron Spectroscopic Investigations of Carbon Monoxide, Nitrogen and Oxygen Adsorbed on Transition Metals[†]

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Carbon monoxide and nitrogen adsorb both molecularly and dissociatively on transition metals. Electron states of CO and N₂ molecularly adsorbed on metals have been studied by uv photoelectron spectroscopy. The bond order of adsorbed CO is between two and three both in the linear and bridged species. Oxygen dissociates on all metals except Pt, Ag and Au, the bond order of molecularly adsorbed oxygen on these metals being between 0.5 and 1.0. Electron states of molecularly adsorbed O₂ have been examined by uv photoelectron spectroscopy. The metal d orbitals donate electrons to the π^* orbitals of oxygen while the π orbital of oxygen donates electrons to the metal.

THE nature of bonding between adsorbed molecules and solid surfaces can be effectively investigated by employing techniques of electron spectroscopy. Thus, ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (uvps) directly provides information on the molecular orbitals of the adsorbed species, while high resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) yields information on the vibrational frequencies of the adsorbed molecules. EELS employing high energy electrons is useful in obtaining information on the electronic transitions of the adsorbed molecules. Besides these techniques of electron spectroscopy, temperature programmed desorption (TPD) has been employed to identify the adsorbed species while EELD has been useful in determining the surface structure. In this article, we discuss the adsorption of three diatomic molecules, carbon monoxide, nitrogen and oxygen, on transition metal surfaces as examined by electron spectroscopic techniques. It was our interest to obtain an unified understanding of the adsorption behaviour of these three molecules. While both carbon monoxide and nitrogen are known to adsorb on transition metals both molecularly (associatively) as well as dissociatively depending on the conditions and the metal, oxygen is almost always adsorbed dissociatively on metals. It is of importance to understand the nature of bonding between these molecules and metal surfaces since this information is of great relevance to catalysis and other surface phenomena.

Experimental

All the electron spectroscopic studies were carried out with an ESCA spectrometer of VG Scientific Ltd., U.K., fitted with a sample preparation chamber and a gas handling manifold. Foils of transition metals of better than 99.9% purity

were etched with argon ions under UHV conditions and it was ensured that the surface concentration of impurities like carbon and oxygen was negligible. Exposure of the metals to CO, N₂ and O₂ was made in the sample preparation chamber to the desired extent before the spectra were recorded. Exposures are referred to in langmuirs, L (1L=10⁻⁶ Torr.sec). The temperature of the sample could be varied by using a special probe designed for the purpose.

Results and Discussions

Carbon monoxide: Carbon monoxide readily chemisorbs on all metals both dissociatively and molecularly¹⁻¹¹; molecular adsorption occurs with a variety of geometries. In Fig. 1 we show the molecular orbital diagram of carbon monoxide in free and adsorbed states. An examination of the molecular orbital picture tells us that the nonbonding 5 σ orbital can be donated to the metal, while the empty 2 π^* antibonding orbital can act as a potential recipient of electrons in the presence of a suitable donor like a metal. Fig. 1 also gives us the picture of a carbon monoxide molecule sitting on a nickel atom. Such a donor-acceptor mechanism of bond formation¹⁰ leads to important consequences. The 5 σ level is stabilized as a consequence of bonding while the back bonding into the 2 π^* level weakens the carbon-oxygen bond leading to a larger separation between the 1 π and 4 σ bonding orbitals. The net effect is to bring the 5 σ and 1 π orbitals of molecularly adsorbed carbon monoxide close to each other (see Fig. 1). Since only valence orbitals are involved in this chemisorption phenomenon, we can employ ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy to characterize the adsorbed species.

We have carried out uvps studies of CO adsorbed on several transition metals. Fig. 2 gives the

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Fig. 1. Mechanism of CO chemisorption on transition metals.

Fig. 2. Valence band of Ni exposed to CO at 300 K. The spectrum shows peaks due to molecular CO.

ultraviolet photoelectron spectrum of molecularly chemisorbed carbon monoxide on polycrystalline nickel. We see two bands here at 7.5 eV and 11.0 eV. The first band corresponds to the unresolvable ($1\pi + 5\sigma$) level of the adsorbed carbon monoxide, while the second is due to the 4σ level. Angular distribution of photoelectrons has provided a basis for these assignments of bands in uvps¹². The binding energy of the 5σ orbital¹³ is found to drastically vary with the heats of adsorption of carbon monoxide on different metals (Fig. 3) showing thereby that the stronger the metal-carbon bond, the greater is the stabilization of the 5σ orbital of the adsorbed molecule.

Fig. 3. Variation of the binding energy of 5σ (CO) orbital with the heat of adsorption for CO chemisorbed on: 1, Cu(311); 2, Pt(100); 3, W(100) and Ni(111); 4, Ni(110) and 5, Pd(100) and Ni(100).

EELS throws some light on the antibonding orbital of adsorbed carbon monoxide. Although there is no direct method of measuring the $2\pi^*$ orbital energy of adsorbed molecules, EELS employing high energy electron beams, gives us the ($5\sigma, 1\pi \rightarrow 2\pi^*$) excitation energy, E_T ; since ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy gives us the 5σ binding energy, we can correlate the difference ($E_T - 5\sigma$), which is a good estimate of the π^* orbital energy, with the enthalpy of adsorption ΔH_{ads} (Fig. 4). Interestingly, this plot parallels the variation in the metal $d \rightarrow 2\pi^*(CO)$ charge transfer energy, which should also reflect the shifting of the π^* orbital on adsorption¹⁴.

Fig. 4. Relation between the $\pi^*(CO)$ orbital energy and the heat of adsorption for CO adsorbed on metals: (1) Cu(311); (2) Pt(111) and Pt(100); (3) W(100); (4) Ni(111), Ni(110); (6) Pd(100) and (7) Ni(100).

High resolution EELS employing low energy electrons throws light on the stereochemistry of the adsorbent-adsorbate system. In addition to giving the carbon-oxygen stretching frequencies, EELS also gives us the metal-carbon stretching frequencies and the subject has been reviewed extensively by Rao *et al*¹⁵. Specific ranges of carbon-oxygen stretching frequencies can be assigned to the different adsorption sites as can be seen from the assignments of Sheppard and Nguyen¹⁶ given below:

$$1880-1650 \text{ cm}^{-1} B_3(111) > B_4(100) > B_5(110)^*$$

$$2000-1880 \text{ cm}^{-1} B_2(111) > B_2(100) > B_2(110)$$

2130–2000 cm^{-1} $C_b(111) > C_r(100)$
 >2130 cm^{-1} oxidized metal surface

Here, B refers to a bridged site and C to a linear site. The subscript in the case of B stands for the number of atoms involved in bridging and subscripts in the case of C sites stand for the coordination of the metal atom.

In the case of linearly adsorbed carbon monoxide molecules, the carbon-oxygen stretching frequency decreases as the metal-carbon stretching frequency increases as one would expect. The carbon-oxygen stretching frequency can also be related to the enthalpy of adsorption, ΔH_{ads} (Fig. 5a). The carbon-oxygen stretching frequency falls as the heat of adsorption becomes more and more exothermic. We can relate the carbon-oxygen stretching frequency with the bond order as well (Fig. 5b). From this correlation we see that linearly adsorbed carbon monoxide molecules have an average bond order close to 3.0 while those on the bridged B_2 site have a bond order closer to 2.4.

Fig. 5. (a) Relation between C-O and the enthalpy of adsorption, ΔH_{ads} for CO adsorbed on transition metal (100) surfaces.

5. (b) Variation of the carbon-oxygen (C-O) stretching frequency with the bond order. Regions for both bridged and linear species are indicated.

According to Broden *et al*, transition metals to the left of the periodic table have a tendency to

chemisorb carbon monoxide dissociatively, while the metals towards the right and bottom of the periodic table adsorb carbon monoxide in a molecular fashion¹⁷. Broden *et al* draw a borderline in the periodic table, to the left of which carbon monoxide is chemisorbed dissociatively, while it is molecularly chemisorbed towards the right. Such a classification, however, is far from comprehensive, as it explains chemisorption processes occurring at room temperature and low temperatures only. Adsorption at higher temperatures cannot be simply classified in this manner. Thus, cobalt and nickel, which lie to the right of this borderline, are found to dissociate carbon monoxide at higher temperature, around 400 K and Cu at 500 K¹¹. Employing the enthalpy of adsorption ΔH_{ads} as a parameter, Benziger¹⁸ has listed the enthalpies of dissociative and molecular chemisorptions of carbon monoxide on different metals; dissociative chemisorption becomes more and more exothermic towards the left of the periodic table, while towards the right and bottom, it becomes less and less exothermic; indeed it is endothermic (Fig. 6). We would therefore expect metals towards the right to chemisorb carbon monoxide molecularly as their heats of molecular chemisorption are exothermic. Consideration of ΔH_{ads} alone, however, becomes untenable at higher temperatures, when entropy factors may outweigh enthalpy factors and a competition between the minimization of enthalpy and the maximization of entropy sets in. Such competitive factors determine a threshold temperature, above which dissociation sets in even though ΔH_{ads} forbids it¹⁸. Below the threshold temperature, dissociation is too slow. At this point we should note that the nature of chemisorption depends only on the electronic structure of the metal; the surface geometry of the adsorbent is relatively unimportant and becomes significant only in the case of metals close to the borderline.

Ti -572	V -410	Cr -335	Mn -279	Fe -136 (-105)	Co -90 (-103)	Ni -88 (-109)	Cu +21 (-71)
Zr 618	Nb -437	Mo 185	Te	Ru > 0 (-124)	Rh > +19 (-130)	Pd > +25 (-142)	Ag +334 (-27)
Hf -667	Ta -469	W -215 (-88)	Re > 68 (-115)	Os > +12	Ir > +25 (-146)	Pt > +110 (-127)	Au > +164 (-58)

Fig. 6. Enthalpies of dissociative and molecular (in parenthesis) chemisorption of carbon monoxide on different transition metals.

In a recent study employing Auger electron spectroscopy¹⁹, it has been found that carbon monoxide is dissociatively adsorbed on Ta, Nb and Ti but molecularly chemisorbed on Pd, Pt and Ir. We find that dissociated carbon monoxide shows XPS binding energies of C(1s) and O(1s) in the same range as those of metal carbides and oxides.

Under conditions of molecular adsorption, disproportionation of carbon monoxide, according to Boudouard reaction, $2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$, has been observed on transition metal surfaces¹¹. Such a reaction leads to a larger build up of surface and subsurface carbon, than a mere dissociation reaction would do. This carbon build up can be readily monitored by Auger and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopies. The carbon build up is quite understandable in the light of the reaction between the gas phase CO and adsorbed CO by the Eley-Rideal mechanism.

Nitrogen: Nitrogen is known to adsorb on transition metals both molecularly and dissociatively. The bonding scheme for molecularly adsorbed nitrogen is similar to that of carbon monoxide adsorption, the two molecules being isoelectronic. We took special interest in the study of nitrogen adsorption on Fe, as previous studies²⁰ on this system employed X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy only. UV photoelectron spectra of the previous studies invariably showed features due to carbon monoxide contamination. Fig. 7 shows the uv photoelectron spectra of nitrogen and carbon monoxide on iron recorded by us. The spectra clearly bring out the differences between molecularly adsorbed nitrogen and carbon monoxide as can be seen from the table below :

		5σ	1π	4σ
CO	free	14.0	16.8	19.7
	adsorbed	8.3	6.2	11.3
N ₂	free	15.6	16.7	18.8
	adsorbed	8.0	6.5	11.0

UV photoelectron spectra upto 173 K clearly show three features at 6.5, 8.0 and 11.0 eV which can be clearly assigned to molecularly adsorbed nitrogen. The 6.5 and 8.0 eV peaks are due to $1\pi+5\sigma$ levels, while the 11.0 eV peak is due to the 4σ level. Accompanying the development of these peaks in the valence region, we find that the intensity of the N(1s) signal in the X-ray photoelectron spectrum increases. The intensities of the C(1s) and O(1s) peaks are essentially constant during the adsorption of nitrogen suggesting that the peaks in the valence region are definitely due to nitrogen. Furthermore, the uv photoelectron spectroscopic bands of carbon monoxide adsorbed on iron (Fig. 7) and recorded under similar conditions are found to be at different positions ; in the case of carbon monoxide, we see a peak at 7.2 eV which is a composite band arising from 1π and 5σ levels ; the second peak of carbon monoxide arises from the 4σ level.

Fig. 8 shows the N(1s) bands in X-ray photoelectron spectra recorded during nitrogen adsorption on Fe for different exposures. Below 20L exposure at 80K, we see two peaks around 400 eV and 403-404 eV arising from two species of nitrogen-linear and bridged²⁰. As we increase the temperature we see a peak appearing around 397 eV as can

Fig. 7. UV Photoelectron (UPE) spectra of carbon monoxide and nitrogen adsorbed on Fe.

Fig. 8. N(1s) peaks in X-ray photoelectron spectra of the Fe + N₂ system.

be seen from the spectrum taken at 298 K. This is due to dissociated nitrogen. Nitrogen also, like carbon monoxide, is adsorbed dissociatively at high-temperatures.

High resolution EELS of nitrogen adsorbed on W shows various loss peaks : at 2120 cm^{-1} due to the nitrogen-nitrogen stretching frequency of the linear molecularly adsorbed species, 1440 cm^{-1} due to the nitrogen-nitrogen stretch of the nitrogen bridge bonded to two W atoms. The metal-nitrogen stretching frequencies for these two modes are seen at 480 cm^{-1} and 600 cm^{-1} respectively²¹.

The nitrogen-nitrogen bond order in the linearly adsorbed species is slightly lower than that of molecular nitrogen, while the bridged species has a bond order close to 2.

Although most transition metals are inert to adsorption of nitrogen, Broden *et al*¹⁷ have proposed that those to the left of the periodic table have a tendency to dissociate the weakly held molecularly physisorbed γ states into the more strongly bound β states, which are thought to be the products of dissociative adsorption. This is verified by soft X-ray appearance potential spectroscopy in which the low coverage N(1s) spectra on Ti and Cr resemble those of atomic nitrogen while the higher coverage N(1s) spectra resemble those of metal nitrides²². Transition metals that lie to the right of the periodic table simply desorb the molecular γ states on heating²³. The same borderline as that drawn for carbon monoxide appears to hold good for nitrogen as well. Benziger¹⁸ has calculated the relevant enthalpies of adsorption (dissociative as well as molecular) and these data are depicted in Fig. 9 to support the classification of nitrogen adsorption on transition metals.

Ti -672	V -434	Cr -246	Mn -256	Fe -22	Co +16	Ni +2	Cu +148
Zr -730	Nb -510	Mo -138	Te	Ru > 0	Rh > 0	Pd 0	Ag +510
Hf -738	Ta -542	W -80	Re > 0	Os > 0	Ir > 0	Pt 0	Au > +54

Fig. 9. Enthalpies of dissociatively chemisorbed nitrogen on different transition metals.

Oxygen: Unlike carbon monoxide and nitrogen discussed above, oxygen had been found to chemisorb only atomically on almost all metals until very recently^{24,25}. It was recently pointed out that molecular oxygen is stable at low temperatures (typically about 100 K) on silver and platinum surfaces. In an attempt to base our conclusions on thermodynamic considerations, we calculated the enthalpy of dissociative adsorption of oxygen

Ti -912	V -836	Cr -752	Mn -770	Fe -534	Co 478	Ni -488	Cu -326
Zr -1080	Nb -812	Mo -544	Te	Ru -220	Rh 182	Pd -170	Ag 62
Hf -1134	Ta -834	W -570	Re -356	Os -196	Ir 168	Pt	Au +54

Fig 10. Enthalpies of dissociatively chemisorbed oxygen on different transition metals.

on different metals following the procedure of Benziger¹⁸. We readily see that metals towards the left of the periodic table show larger exothermic heats of dissociative chemisorption (Fig. 10). The most striking feature is the fact that, while all metals at 298 K exhibit exothermic heats of dissociative adsorption (even Ag and Pt), only gold shows a positive heat of dissociative adsorption. We have to come to the obvious conclusion that gold must adsorb oxygen molecularly at least at low temperatures. These considerations tempted us to classify adsorption of oxygen on metals as in Fig. 10.

In order to investigate electron states of molecularly adsorbed oxygen on metals and also to give credence to our classification in Fig. 10, we have carried out low temperature uv photoelectron spectroscopic studies on oxygen adsorbed on silver and gold. He II uv photoelectron spectra of clean and oxygen covered silver are shown in Fig. 11. We see

Fig. 11. UV Photoelectron (He II) spectra of oxygen chemisorbed on polycrystalline silver. Positions of bands in free O₂ are indicated by a bar diagram.

peaks at 6.0 eV, 9.8 eV and a broad peak from 11.5-14.3 which compare well with the gas phase oxygen molecule. Together with the development of these

peaks, we observed a large increase in the oxygen (1s) signal in the XPS (Fig 12). At lower exposures, we see a peak at 532.7 eV, which can be assigned to the molecular oxygen species. A lower binding energy peak at 531.7 eV is due to atomic oxygen due to initial dissociation of molecular oxygen. At higher temperature (300 K) we see only the lower binding energy peak at 529.7 eV due to chemisorbed atomic oxygen. The molecular species has clearly desorbed.

Fig. 12. X-ray photoelectron spectra showing O(1s) bands for Ag+O₂ system.

We have just completed preliminary uv photoelectron spectroscopic studies of oxygen adsorbed on gold and have established for the first time that oxygen can be molecularly adsorbed on gold at low temperatures (~150 K). On heating, the molecular species appears to desorb.

High resolution EELS of molecular oxygen chemisorbed on metals^{24,25} shows two vibrational frequencies at 240 cm⁻¹ and 640 cm⁻¹ in case of silver and 390 cm⁻¹ and 870 cm⁻¹ in case of platinum. The lower vibrational frequency in both cases are due to the metal-oxygen stretch while the higher frequency is due to oxygen-oxygen stretch. These low oxygen-oxygen stretching frequencies are clearly indicative of the weakening of the O-O bond on adsorption, partly due to donation of the metal electrons to the π* orbitals of oxygen. Based on the calculation of Backx *et al*²⁴, we can estimate (Fig. 13) the population in the π* orbital of the adsorbed oxygen to be 3.7 and 3.3 in the case of silver and platinum systems respectively. The oxygen-oxygen stretching frequency in the case of silver is much lower than that of a oxygen-oxygen single bond (as in peroxides) suggesting that there should be a mechanism for further lowering of the bond order

Fig. 13. Correlation of ν(O-O) stretching frequencies with the number of electrons in the π* orbital. MO diagram of O₂ adsorbed on metals is also shown.

of oxygen besides that due to metal d→π* charge transfer. This can arise from donation of oxygen π electrons to the metal. We can estimate the electron configuration of oxygen adsorbed on metals by considering the relationship between the oxygen-oxygen stretching frequencies and bond order (Fig. 14). We see that the bond order in the case of silver is around 0.8 while it is 1.0 in the case of platinum. Assuming that lowering of the oxygen-oxygen bond order from that of a single bond is due to donation of π electrons from oxygen to metal and taking the π* population to be between 3.5 and 4.0, the electron configuration of oxygen adsorbed on transition metals can be written as (π_g)² 5-4 u (π*_g)² 5-4 o.

Fig. 14. Correlation of ν(O-O) stretching frequencies with the bond order.

Temperature programmed desorption after oxygen adsorption on platinum at low temperatures shows two peaks, one at 150 K and the other at 800 K. The former is due to desorption of molecular oxygen, while the latter is due to desorption of atomic oxygen²⁵. Clearly the low temperature molecular desorption is accompanied by atomisation. Indeed it is believed that molecular desorption sets in due to

atomisation. On atomisation, the atomic oxygen needs twice the number of sites than the molecular oxygen and hence a portion of the molecular oxygen desorbs. At low coverages, the presence of several empty sites causes a significant entropy factor to force dissociation at temperatures lower than the temperature of molecular desorption. Putting these data together we can draw an imaginary phase diagram for the platinum-oxygen system (Fig. 15). At low temperatures, we have molecular oxygen; but in addition, at low coverages, we have some atomic oxygen as well. Beyond a certain threshold temperature, dissociation sets in and only atomic oxygen can be found on the surface. At still higher temperatures, we have the formation of bulk oxide layers.

Fig. 15. Imaginer phase diagram of a Metal + O_2 system, plotted as a function of initial coverage.

Concluding remarks : Both carbon monoxide and nitrogen adsorb molecularly on surfaces of many transition metals and undergo dissociation on certain metals. The tendency to dissociate can be rationalized on the basis of the enthalpies of adsorption. When these molecules adsorb molecularly, the bond order falls to a value between 2.0 and 3.0.

Unlike carbon monoxide and nitrogen, oxygen adsorbs on transition metals almost always dissociatively and where the thermodynamics of dissociative adsorption is unfavourable, it adsorbs molecularly at

low temperatures, Pt, Ag and Au being the only three such metals. Molecularly adsorbed oxygen is associated with a bond order between 0.5 and 1.0.

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